

PROTECTING THE RIGHT TO WATER IN PALESTINE IN ISLAMIC SHARIA AND LAW

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Abstract

Water resources constitute an important place within the concerns of the international community in the modern era, why not and all indications suggest that future conflicts and conflicts in the world will be about controlling water resources and ensuring their survival, in light of a terrible climate change that has negatively affected water resources, especially fresh ones. The international scene today clearly shows the great movement of the international community in order to ensure the legal protection of water resources and to distance them from armed conflicts, in addition to resolving the various conflicts that were caused by water in amicable ways that guarantee each party their right to water without wasting the right of generations. The next. And the problem is to answer the main question: How was it possible to protect the water rights in Palestine, especially the Gaza Strip, in accordance with Islamic Sharia and the law? Several questions derive from this main question. What is the concept of the right to water in Islamic law and law? As well as the next question of what is the reality of the right to water in Palestine? The next question is what are the ways to protect the right to water in Islamic Sharia and law?

Search Plan

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Introduction

Water is the basis of life, and on it is the orbit of all other environmental elements, and this is indicated by the Almighty's saying (And we made from water every living thing. Will they not then believe) Surat Al-Anbiya: verse 30

The verse indicated that the water element is the common denominator among all living things, and it is an important element in the creativity, nourishment and development of every living thing - whether human, animal or plant. Punish each other through it and use it as a political blackmail card. These behaviors continue to our present era, in which various barbaric weapons and tools have been used in wars such as nuclear, biological and chemical bombs, causing massive destruction of water resources and a great devastation to the environment and its components, the most important of which is water. The right to water is classified as a human right no less important than other rights mentioned in international documents and declarations of human rights such as the right to life, the right to physical integrity, the right to health, the right to education, and the right to housing. The Palestinian legislator defined the right to water as follows: "Every person

has the right to obtain his need of drinking water of appropriate quality for use, at specific prices in accordance with a tariff system issued by the Council of Ministers.” As for the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), the right to water has been defined. that: each person has a source of water; The latter (water) is required to be safe, in sufficient quantity, and at an appropriate price; In order for a person to live a healthy, dignified and productive life, while at the same time preserving ecosystems that help restore water production, and in the same context, the United Nations Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights defined the right to water as the right of everyone to: of water that is sufficient, safe, acceptable, physically accessible and financially affordable for personal and domestic use.” Among the international conventions and legal principles that should be observed during armed conflicts, including the protection of water resources from all forms of encroachment during various political and armed conflicts, and perhaps the most important of these conventions were the four Geneva Conventions that were concluded in 1949 in addition to the two protocols attached to them, which were signed in 1977 and what they included There are explicit and direct provisions that guarantee the legal protection of water during armed conflicts.

The first topic: the concept and reality of the right to water in Islamic Sharia and law

Water is one of the natural wealth and basic resources of countries. It is used in various fields in the country in the field of domestic use, sanitation, agriculture, industry and trade. Competition for water resources exists within the country itself between different sectors.

How then is the competition between states over this vital resource that does not tolerate armed conflict because it is the basic element that the individual and states need for the continuation of life?

The first requirement: the concept and importance of water in Palestine

The issue of water in Palestine is an essential part and component of the Palestinian economic, social and political fabric. Water and land represent the main component of sovereignty, and the important element to ensure effective independence. Water is the lifeblood and lifeline, and any deficiency of this element leads to a real disaster. In some cases, water availability or interruption becomes a matter of life or death. Therefore, the United Nations General Assembly affirms the right to clean water as an inalienable human right.

Many specialized international studies have indicated that the issue of water shortage and the low quality of available water is one of the most important environmental and economic issues that occupy the Middle East region, and is also seen as one of the most important issues in the final solution negotiations between the Palestinian and Israeli sides, and therefore, the rights will be Water in Palestine is the most important challenge facing the Palestinian state, as a result of the continuous and systematic Israeli violations of water rights in Palestine and the deprivation of millions of Palestinian residents from enjoying their right to water or disposing of the minimum of their natural right to it, which is supposed to be guaranteed by laws, international agreements, human rights organizations and peace treaties. .

The second requirement: the reality of water in Palestine

Since Israel's occupation of the Palestinian territories in 1967, the occupying power has controlled all water sources, both surface and underground, as it issued a series of military orders according to which water was made state property, and it is not allowed to use it except with special permits granted by the military ruler.

This control continued despite the change in the political situation that accompanied the mutual recognition between the Palestine Liberation Organization and Israel, and the signing of the Declaration of Principles Agreement in September 1993 (Oslo 1 - Gaza - Jericho first) (according to which the Palestinian National Authority was declared with its existing institutions and with legal jurisdiction over each of the West Bank West Bank and the Gaza Strip, except for areas that include settlements (Area C) in the West Bank and areas occupied by settlements in the Gaza Strip prior to the unilateral disengagement, which Israel evacuated from the Strip in 2005.

The term of the interim agreement was five years, during which it was supposed to reach a just and comprehensive solution to the core issues of the conflict: borders, refugees, settlements, Jerusalem, and water rights.

With regard to Palestinian rights to water, the file was dealt with in the Interim Agreement (Oslo 2) in Article 40 of Annex III (Protocol of Economic Cooperation to the Interim Agreement entitled (Water and Sewage)), according to which Israel recognized Palestinian water rights in the West Bank; The understanding on this was postponed to final status negotiations. Under this clause, a total of 118 million cubic meters were allocated to the Palestinian side from the existing sources (springs and wells) in the West Bank; It was supposed to enable the Palestinian side to dig wells that would add to the total being used, an additional 80 million cubic meters of the three West Bank basins.

The lack of sufficient quantities of water for Palestinian citizens is a permanent problem, in addition to the problem of water pollution in the Gaza Strip, which is greater than in the West Bank, all due to Israeli policies and practices based on discrimination, deprivation, and exploitation of Palestinian water resources.

This is reflected in the significant disparity in access to water between Israelis and Palestinians, as the consumption of water per capita in the State of Palestine is about 72 liters per capita per day, (much less than the level recommended by the World Health Organization of 100 liters per capita per day); The average Israeli per capita consumption of water is about 300 liters per day; That is, it increases by about four times.

Since the occupation of the Palestinian territories in 1967, Israel has been working to deprive the Palestinian people of their rights to water; numerous military orders have been issued, which, in their entirety, provide for Israel's absolute freedom of action in Palestinian waters.

In implementation of these orders, Israel took a number of measures and practices, such as:

- 1 -Setting a limit on the amount of water that well owners are allowed to pump in the West Bank and Gaza Strip, so that it does not exceed 100 cubic metres.

2 -Preventing the drilling of new wells for agricultural purposes, and placing restrictions on them, especially in border areas

3 -Confiscation of Palestinian farmers' wells for the benefit of the Israeli settlements...

4 -Theft of large quantities of Palestinian water, by digging many wells in the Israeli settlements, which causes large quantities of water to flow from inside the aquifer from the eastern Gaza Strip, to the Israeli wells dug at very great depths.

5 -The Israeli government's refusal to give the amount of water specified in the peace agreements to the governorates of the West Bank and Gaza Strip.

6 -Israel has contributed significantly to the pollution of groundwater, by continuously draining public sewage from settlement areas to sandy areas and valleys; what causes it to seep into the aquifer water and pollute it, and direct drainage is done by pipes, or through containers with portable pumps to transport it to large valleys.

The wastewater infrastructure, which was neglected during the years before the arrival of the National Authority since the outbreak of the second intifada, was exposed to the escalation of Israeli attacks, which resulted in its destruction in many areas as a result of the incursions carried out by the occupation forces, as they destroyed the main and subsidiary lines in the water networks. Wastewater, in addition to the bombing of wastewater treatment plants, which led to their complete destruction or severe damage

The second topic: The right to water in Sharia and law

The first requirement: the right to water in Islamic law

First: The necessity of water in life:

Water is the basis of life, and on it is the orbit of all other environmental elements, and this is indicated by the Almighty's saying (And we made from water every living thing. Will they not then believe) Surat Al-Anbiya: verse 30, and the verse clarified that the element of water is the common denominator among all living things, and it is an important element in Creativity, nourishment and development of every living thing - whether human, animal or plant - that is: everything in the universe that is characterized by growth does not need water, otherwise it will be subject to annihilation and destruction. The first is appreciation and consideration, and he mentioned that it is used for medicine as it came in the Sunnah on the authority of Aisha, may God be pleased with her, on the authority of the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, he said:

"Fever is from the heat of Hell, so cool it with water".

This is a statement from the Prophet for the use of water in medicine, and therefore we find the use of compresses to reduce human temperature, and Islam considered it one of the most important wealth

And as in the hadith, Uthman said: The Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, said:

“Whoever buys a well in Rumah, then his bucket therein will be like the buckets of the Muslims”.

The evidence for this is the emergence of civilizations around the sources of water, and the extinction of some civilizations when it is lost and receded, and many wars have arisen throughout human history because of water, Ali Mustafa al-Qudah, the Prophet’s guidance in protecting water from pollution and its impact on preserving the environment

Second: The necessity of water for worship:

Water has a great place in the Sharia, and therefore we find that the Holy Qur’an linked the worship of man with his repentance, and his forgiveness, and the sending of water, as in the Almighty’s saying.

(Oh people, ask forgiveness from your Lord, then repent to Him, and He will send rain upon you)
Surah Hud: verse 52

And the hadiths came with the reward and reward of caring for water, as in the saying of the Messenger of God, may God’s prayers and peace be upon him (“There are seven whose reward will be passed on to the servant while he is in his grave after his death: whoever learns knowledge, runs a river, digs a well, planted palm trees, builds a mosque, or inherits a Qur’an. Or he left a son asking forgiveness for him after his death)).

What was narrated from the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace:

“Every known is a charity, for it is known that your brother will meet a divorced face, and to empty from your signs in the dependence of your brother.”

Third: The right to water is a common right:

Water God created man and what is in it and subjugated him to man, and he is entrusted in it to benefit from it and use it to build the universe, but his succession in the universe does not mean that he disposes of its resources without responsibility, and water is a common right for all people, and every human being has a right to it, and the Shariah came to explain this matter as In the Almighty’s saying (And tell them that the water is to be shared between them, every drink is dying) Surah Al-Qamar: verse 28, so water is shared among humans, and a general possession in every time and place. It is forbidden: water, pasture, and fire.” In the hadith it is a statement that no one has the right to monopolize the use of water without anyone else. The universe with its various resources is not the property of a generation of generations, but rather it is the permanent heritage of mankind that must be preserved for the benefit of man, and no generation has the right to destroy this resource. It deprives future generations

International law does not include in its standards any explicit formula regulating the right of individuals to water. Nor does this law include any explicit definition of pure water as a collective right that can be claimed. There is no doubt that this situation constitutes a gap in the international legal system, so that it is imperative to work to correct it as soon as possible, as demanded by various international organizations and movements over several years. International water law defines the water rights of neighbouring parties, which includes applicable and specific standards In the Helsinki Rules on the Uses of the Waters of International Rivers of 1966, and the United

Nations Convention on Trans boundary Water Resources of 1997, international water law calls for the allocation of fair and reasonable quantities of water between the parties or parties that have a claim to the shared water resources. The right to water an individual human right, and the United Nations Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights has noted that “the human right to water is indispensable for living in dignity, and is a prerequisite and prerequisite for the realization of other human rights”.

Relevant legal instruments include the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966. Article 6 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, which has been signed and ratified by over 130 A state, including Israel, that "the right to life is an inherent right of every human being. The law must protect this right." As for the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, in its first article, it declares the right of “all peoples to freely dispose of their wealth and natural resources”.

It is worth noting that the customary legal rules lack the necessary force in essence, as they lack the regulatory force that would reach mandatory and punish the aggressors in case of violation of international law. These legal provisions also lack the main feature that distinguishes the law, which is the ability to implement its provisions in an obligatory manner, like other basic rights in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations. Explicitly, but this does not prevent us from extracting some important legal principles that regulate the management of water resources from the regulations annexed to the Fourth Convention of 1970 issued by the Hague Conference. Water Perhaps the connection of water resources with politics in the Arab world began with the emergence of political borders between states and the conflict began between neighbouring states over a common water resource, whether surface or underground. States compete to obtain rights, resulting in scarce ownership of water resources between countries, becoming a resource and political tensions There is an international rule that allows the state to have complete control over its resources, but with regard to water resources, there is a difference that a group of states participate in them because rivers, seas and even groundwater penetrate several states as they originate from one and flow into another, so political conflicts arise due to the exploitation of one state by another aquatic.

The Right as a New Social Right: Realistically, we have to take into account that clean drinking water - unlike sea water, sunlight and outer space - is not a "natural good", let alone a universal good that can be considered a "natural right." regardless of the legal meaning of this last expression. In fact, what is considered today a basic human need, the right to water as representing the right to survival is a right to social solidarity - as is the case with the right to health, education and housing - which requires the political community to make great efforts in this context.

.The right to water as a collective right: In my view, the right to water should be seen as a “collective right”. In this context, I use the term "collective right" - a concept largely alien to Western theory of human rights - in the sense it has acquired since the 1993 United Nations conference in Vienna.

The third topic: the legal protection of water in Palestine

The first requirement: the legal protection of the right to water

First: Conserving water and protecting it from pollution:

Water damage and pollution is one of the most serious environmental problems that many countries face, especially in Gaza City. Therefore, Islamic Sharia texts urge the preservation of water and its protection from pollution, according to the Almighty's saying.

)Eat and drink from the provision of God, and do not sin on earth, making mischief) Surah Al-Baqarah: verse 60

And in the verse it is forbidden to spoil, and one of the greatest corruption is to pollute the water that is the life of people, and the hadiths came about that as in his saying, may God's prayers and peace be upon him that he forbade to pay attention to stagnant water".

This is evidence of the prohibition of polluting water, and sewage is one of the most pollutants of water, as well as the words of the Messenger of God, may God's prayers and peace be upon him:

"Fear the three curses: excrement in the springs, the side of the road, and the shade".

In the hadith it is forbidden to pollute and spoil the water, and the prohibition requires prohibition.

Second: Prohibition of draining water sources:

The Qur'anic and Prophetic directives clearly and explicitly call for the necessity of moderation and economy, and the proper utilization of water resources, and the problem of fresh water scarcity is a big problem as long as it has led to many conflicts.

)Eat and drink, and do not be extravagant, for He does not like the wasteful) Surah Al-A'raf: verse 30.

What was mentioned in the hadith is that the Messenger of God, May God bless him and grant him peace, passed by Sa'd while he was performing ablution, and he said: "What is this extravagance"?

"Yes, and if you are on a running river,

In the hadith it is forbidden to waste water and extravagance, and this prohibition is not limited to a state of drought or scarcity, as well as what was stated that the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, used to take a bath, with sa' to five times, and with water in the morning. Worships, which are prayer, so what is sufficient to achieve the validity of the prayer is sufficient.

And if saving water is required in purification, then it is a fortiori in ordinary uses, and Al-Shawkani transmitted the consensus of the jurists on avoiding extravagance with water, even if it is on the river bank, and he went to the Shafi'i prohibition of that.

Third: The State's Role in Protecting the Right to Water:

It is the duty of the rulers to intervene in order to achieve the public interests, and to ward off corruption even if the texts do not state that it is positive or prohibited according to the sent interests. This is due to the legal rules of the rule (the imam's behavior on the subjects is dependent on the interest), and accordingly the state may establish legislation that ensures water conservation, and take measures and procedures related to preventing water waste or pollution based on the rules of preventing harm and blocking pretexts.

That the Palestinian territories are part of the countries of the world, they are threatened as is the case in other countries, but the specificity of the Palestinian situation is more complicated than the rest of the countries in the region, as the Palestinian territories do not constitute a single geographical unit, in addition to the continuous Israeli violations of Palestinian water rights, Tightening Israel's control over wells and aquifers, and preventing the Palestinians from digging new wells.

Protecting the environment in times of armed conflict is a principle adopted by many international instruments such as the first Geneva Additional Protocol to the Geneva Conventions, which prohibits military operations that would harm the environment for long periods. For military objectives or any other hostile objectives, approved by the United Nations through the General Assembly on December 10, 1976 under No. 72/31, in addition to the fact that the destruction or aggression against the natural environment during armed conflicts is not justified by military necessity, but rather is a violation of the provisions of international law According to the provisions of Articles 23, Paragraph (g) of the Fourth Hague Convention, Articles 53 and 147 of the Fourth Geneva Convention, and Articles 35/3 and 55 of Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions.

The pollution of the waters of the ecological zones includes fresh water of all kinds, as well as touches the underground water or the so-called groundwater, and the United Nations has paid great attention to the issue of environmental protection in times of armed conflict and stated in the general principles of the World Charter on the Environment that: "Nature must be Safe from deterioration caused by war or other hostile activities, therefore, water resources and associated water facilities, which are part of the environment, have been the subject of protection in the rules of international humanitarian law, and all parties to armed conflict must abide by these provisions for the common benefit of humanity and its common good, as The second article of the thirty-first paragraph of the Gaza-Jericho Agreement dealt with the issue of water, and specific powers over water were transferred to the Palestinian Authority, without the agreement dealing with water rights in detail. The water sector, water resources management, implementation of water policies, and supervision and control of water projects in both the West Bank to West Bank and the Gaza Strip, and to follow up on the implementation of what was stated in Article 40, and to exploit the quantities of water allocated to the Palestinians in the agreement, as it was entrusted with preparing for final status negotiations, to ensure and maintain the Palestinian water rights stipulated in the Interim Phase Agreement.

The most important sources of water in the Gaza Strip is the coastal basin, which lies below the coast of the Mediterranean Sea between Rafah in the south and the Carmel mountains in the north. Its total area is 2,200 km², of which there are 400 km² under the Gaza Strip. The occupation state's digging of many water "fisheries" wells, in addition to the increase in the population in the Strip to about 2 million Palestinians living in Gaza and in an area not exceeding 360 square kilometers, is one of the most important reasons for withdrawing the aquifer, and consequently, the increase in salinity to more than Four times.

Humanitarian law aims to guarantee the minimum conditions suitable for a normal life, and humane treatment is the basis for the ordinary, for the persons it is supposed to protect. This life becomes a tangible reality in the event that the primary needs of human beings are met, and access to safe water is one of the most important of these needs. The second paragraph of Article (12) of Additional Protocol I, the Geneva Conventions, stipulates that: It is prohibited to attack, destroy, move or disrupt objects and materials. Which are indispensable for the survival of the civilian population, for example, foodstuffs, agricultural areas that produce them, crops, livestock, drinking water facilities and their networks, and irrigation works, if the intent is to prevent them from the civilian population or the adversary for their vital value, regardless of the motive, whether with the intention of starving civilians or to force them to flee or to another motive

The various sources that are relied upon to provide legal protection for water resources during armed conflicts in international law, as it was noted that international law has been approved in its various sources for the necessary protection of water resources, according to principles that have been stipulated and adopted as a legal rule that must be adhered to during armed conflicts, especially the principle of protection Civilian objects that are indispensable to civilians, in addition to preventing the targeting or destruction of any engineering works or installations containing dangerous forces that could affect civilians in times of armed conflict, up to the principle of protecting the natural environment from the raging of armed conflicts.

The first requirement: the principle of protecting civilian objects, which are indispensable to humans

International humanitarian law is guaranteed by the various provisions of the Third and Fourth Geneva Conventions of 1949; the right to have access to safe drinking water and sanitation facilities. This right was accompanied by the right to health and the concept of public health, but it did not provide protection for water networks and irrigation works, which means that protection was not primarily directed at these objects per se, but rather on the persons protected under this law.

The relationship of civilian objects to water resources is evident in the fact that these objects enjoy protection; Given that they are considered purely civil property, including the protection of water facilities and civil institutions for the supply of potable water during armed conflicts, as every attack on water resources and its various facilities; From the point of view of international humanitarian law, it is considered an illegal act, given that they are civilian objects that derive their protection from international humanitarian law, since they are not considered military targets except in the case of extreme necessity.

The second requirement: protection of works and installations containing dangerous forces

International humanitarian law has ensured through its texts the provision of protection to civilians from the destructive effects of these facilities if they are targeted in armed conflicts, as Article 56 and Article 15 respectively of the two Additional Protocols to the four Geneva Conventions of 1977 dealt with this matter, as the two Additional Protocols established the legal protection of engineering works And installations that contain dangerous forces, just as water resources are an essential source of life, they are also considered a means of lethal warfare, so it was necessary to protect some installations that contain dangerous forces, especially after they became targets for attacks.

The third requirement: the principle of protecting the natural environment and its relationship to water resources

The Fourth Geneva Convention of 1949, relating to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War, states: On the prohibition of the destruction of immovable or movable property in accordance with Article 53 of the same Convention, which provides a minimum level of environmental protection during a state of occupation, as Article 55 of Protocol I of 1977 stipulates the following:

1-The natural environment must be protected from widespread and long-term severe damage during armed conflicts, and this protection includes prohibiting the use of methods or means of warfare that are intended or expected to cause such damage to the natural environment, and therefore affect the health and survival of the population on the Alive.

2-Deterrence attacks against the natural environment are prohibited.

Because water resources are an element of the natural environment, they may be affected during armed conflicts due to hostilities, whether intentionally or unintentionally, by the warring parties, which directly affects humans, especially since water has become at the present time one of the main factors for achieving economic and social development.

The conclusion is divided into the most important results and recommendations:

A person's right to water increases the possibility of enjoying his other rights. On the other hand, the absence of a person's enjoyment of this right will create a disturbance in his life. Which leads him to make daily search trips in order to secure this vital element in his life. All of this affects the levels of his benefit from his other rights, such as the right to health, education and food. In this regard, vulnerable groups such as the poor, women, minorities and children are considered among the most sensitive to any imbalance in the water supply.

Results

1. The various sources of international law recognize the necessary protection of water resources
2. The occupying power has taken control of all water sources, surface and underground, as it issued a series of military orders
3. Customary legal rules were devoid of the regulatory force that would reach mandatory and punish the aggressors in case of violation of international law, with regard to the water rights of states and groups.

4. Water is a necessity for life, and it is the orbit of all other environmental elements. Therefore, the Shariah was concerned with the provisions of water
5. Sharia is concerned with water pollution and the depletion of its sources, and the state has a major role in setting preventive measures and the fourth penal measures to protect the right to water.

Recommendations:

1. Increasing interest in environmental awareness by holding seminars and conferences and supporting institutions in the field of environmental protection
2. Establishing cooperation agreements between Islamic countries to distribute water, protect this right, and resolve disputes related to shared waters
3. Preparing programs to educate and train citizens on how to deal with polluted water
4. Activating the role of the authorities responsible for monitoring water quality, and working on documenting the results.
5. Activating the role of state accountability before the relevant state courts to pursue the occupation for looting water in Palestine.

The References:

The Holy Quran

1. Muhammad al-Makki al-Nasiri, d.: 1414 AH, al-Taysir fi Ahadith al-Tafsir, Dar al-Gharb al-Islami, Beirut, 1, 1405 AH, 1085 AD, 4/338,
2. Muhammad bin Ismail Abu Abdullah Al-Bukhari, Sahih Al-Bukhari, investigation: Muhammad Zuhair bin Nasser Al-Nasser, Dar Touq Al-Najat, 1, 1422 AH, 4/121
3. Al-Bukhari: 3/109.
4. Ali Mustafa Al-Qudah, The Prophet's Guidance in Protecting Water from Pollution and Its Effect on Preserving the Environment, Studies of Sharia and Law Sciences, Volume 46, Number 1, 2019, pg: 313.
5. Abu Bakr Ahmed bin Amr bin Abdul Khaliq bin Khallad bin Obaid Allah, known as Al-Bazzar (died: 292 AH), Musnad Al-Bazzar published in the name of Al-Bahr Al-Zakhkhar, investigation: Adel bin Saad, Library of Science and Judgment - Madinah, i.13/483.
6. Muhammad bin Ismail bin Ibrahim bin Al-Mughirah Al-Bukhari, (T.: 256 AH), single literature, investigation: Muhammad Fouad Abdel-Baqi, Dar Al-Bashaer Al-Islamiya - Beirut, 3rd edition, 1409 - 1989, 1/114.
7. "Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Yazid Al-Qazwini, (T.: 273 AH), SunanIbnMajah, investigation: Muhammad Fouad Abdul Baqi.
8. House of Revival of Arabic Books - Faisal Issa Al-Babi Al-Halabi, 2/826.
9. Abu Muhammad Muwaffaq al-Din Abdullah bin Ahmed bin Muhammad bin Qudamah al-Maqdisi, (died: 620 AH), 1388 AH - 1968 AD, 1/151.
10. Hayel Abdel Hafeez, Water Pollution and Depletion, a Legal Study, The Jordanian Journal of Islamic Studies, Volume VII, Issue 3, 1433 AH, 2011 AD.
11. Muslim bin Al-Hajjaj Abu Al-Hasan Al-Qushayri Al-Nisaburi (T.: 261 AH), Sahih Muslim.
12. Investigation: Muhammad FouadAbd al-Baqi, House of Revival of Arab Heritage - Beirut, 1/335.

13. Abu Dawood Suleiman bin Al-Ash'ath bin Ishaq bin Bashir bin Shaddad bin Amr.
14. Investigation: Muhammad Muhyi Al-Din Abdel Hamid, Al-Masaba Al-Asriya, Saida - Beirut, 7/1.
15. Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Yazid Al-Qazwini bin Majah (died: 273 AH), SunanIbnMajah, investigation: Muhammad Fouad Abdul Baqi.
16. House of Revival of Arabic Books - Faisal Issa Al-Babi Al-Halabi, 1/147.
17. Sahih al-Bukhari: 1/51.
18. Muhammad bin Ali Al-Shawkani, Neil Al-Awtar, Dar Ibn Al-Qayyim, Riyadh, Dar IbnAffan N, Cairo, 1st Edition, 2005 AD, 2/79.
19. Muhammad Fathi Al-Derini, Fundamentalist Approaches to Ijtihad and Opinion in Islamic Legislation, Al-Resala Foundation, 1997, p.: 477.
20. Abdul Rahman bin AbiBakr Al-Suyuti (T.: 911 AH), Al-Shabah and Al-Nazaer, International Ideas House, Jordan, p.: 172.
21. Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948)
22. Palestinian Water Law No. (3) of 2002
23. United Nations Development Program: Human Development Report 2006, previous reference, p. 8.
24. United Nations Development Program: "Sustainability and equity, a better future for all", Human Development Report 2011, translated by: United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Western Asia (ESCWA), Virginia: Colocraft of Virginia (2011, p. 75.(
25. United Nations Development Program: "The Millennium Development Goals are a pact between nations to end human poverty." Human Development Report 2003, translated by Ghassan Ghosn, Maria Abu Khalifa, Samer Abu Hawash, Beirut: Karaki Press, 2003, pp. 103-104.
26. United Nations Development Program: Human Development Report 2011, op.cit., pp. 74-75.
27. Mohamed Abdel Raouf Abdel Hamid, "The Right to Water," Environmental Horizons magazine, December 19, issue.